

Positive Discrimination and the Architecture of Constitutional Justice in Ghana: A Reappraisal

Abstract

The 1992 Constitution of Ghana guarantees the right to equality and prohibits discrimination on various grounds. However, the realization of this right remains a challenge in a society marked by deep-seated inequalities. The aim of this paper is to explore the jurisprudential architecture of equality and non-discrimination under the Constitution, with particular focus on the constitutional and legal justification for positive discrimination. Drawing on case law and constitutional analysis, the paper interrogates the boundaries of the right to equality and what properly constitutes “discrimination” under article 17 of the Constitution. It critiques a narrow reading of equality rights and calls for a more liberal interpretation that preserves the sanctity of the principle of equality while accommodating permissible forms of differential treatment in the Ghanaian deeply unequal society. The paper argues that positive discrimination, when properly designed and targeted, is not only legally permissible but necessary in the quest for socio-economic development and constitutional justice. It does, however, caution against indiscriminate differentiation that may worsen rather than dismantle inequality. The paper concludes with a reflection on Ghana’s historical and structural imbalances, and makes the case for a careful, equity-sensitive approach to legislation and adjudication as the country charts its developmental path.

Keywords: Constitution, human rights, equality, discrimination, positive discrimination

Introduction

The enjoyment of human rights and freedoms is a defining characteristic of democratic societies. The fundamental human rights and freedoms of citizens are, therefore, often explicitly enshrined in the Constitution of most constitutional democracies.

Similarly, in Ghana, the fundamental human rights and freedoms of all people are clearly stated under Chapter Five of the 1992 Constitution of Ghana (hereafter referred to as ‘Constitution’). Often referred to as Ghana’s Bill of Rights,¹ this chapter begins with article 12, which enjoins all organs and agencies of government as well as individuals and entities to respect and uphold the human rights and freedoms enshrined therein. Recognizing that these rights and freedoms amply enumerated and guaranteed under the said chapter would be abstract claims if there were no mechanisms for their enforcement, the Constitution goes further by adequately providing for the actualization of the human rights provisions. It clothes the High Court with jurisdiction to enforce the fundamental human rights and freedoms it guarantees.² Therefore, as Adinyira JSC aptly puts it in *Republic vs. Eugene Baffoe-Bonnie and Others*³, “respect for human rights is an attribute or an element of good governance, and all efforts must be made to ensure its observance.”

¹ See *Adjei Ampofo v Attorney General & President of the National House of Chiefs* [2011] 2 SCGLR 1104 (Date-Bah JSC)

² 1992 Constitution of Ghana, Articles 140(2) and 33(1). However, under limited circumstances, the Supreme Court may have jurisdiction to interpret and enforce human rights provisions of the Constitution. See *Adjei-Ampofo (No. 1) v Accra Metropolitan Assembly & Attorney-General (No. 1)* [2007-2008] SCGLR 611

³ *Republic vs. Eugene Baffoe-Bonnie and Others* [2018-2019] 1 GLR 42

The enforcement of human rights and fundamental freedoms is, however, subject to limitations where necessary to safeguard the rights of others and the public interest, as provided under article 12(2) of the Constitution. The rights of the individual are necessarily constrained by the broader interests of society. This is a universally accepted constitutional principle and indeed, every legal system incorporates express or implied limitation clauses to mediate the tension between personal freedoms and societal interests.

The duty of the judge in a democracy is therefore to ensure that neither the imperatives of the state nor the rights of the individual are unduly compromised, but are preserved in a manner that reflects the constitutional order.⁴ The State must be kept from being sacrificed on the altar of human rights. Similarly, the interests of the State should not be prioritized at a disproportionate expense of human rights.

The Right to Equality and Freedom From Discrimination

Equality before the law is one of the three principles outlined by A. V. Dicey as underpinning the doctrine of rule of law.⁵ By this, he meant that the law has no respect for persons regardless of their respective identifications.⁶ This philosophy is based on the belief that all citizens are equals with intrinsic worth and dignity. The equality status is predicated on the idea that “*individuals, as rational beings, in participating in the creation of a just society do so with the anticipation of being entitled to equal respect, equal economic claims, equal opportunities and tolerance.*”⁷

Thus, as a necessary condition to the success of any society, it is expected that there will be equal subjection of all classes to the ordinary law of the land administered by the ordinary law courts and government agencies. The Constitution prohibits disparity in the treatment of persons on the basis of gender, race, colour, ethnicity, religion, creed or social or economic status.⁸ Every individual is entitled to equal protection under the law. This embodies the principle of non-discrimination. It requires that the people possess the right to be treated fairly and not be discriminated against because of their race, colour, gender, language, religion, political beliefs, status or any other unlawful reason. The Committee of Experts, whose report largely influenced the provisions of the Constitution highlighted the significance of non-discrimination in the enjoyment of rights in the following terms:

“Whatever the material scope of these rights, one thing is clear: all persons are entitled to these rights without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, gender, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. This emphasizes the significance and scope of the principle of

⁴ Aharon Barak, *The Judge in a Democracy* (1st edn, Princeton University Press c2006) 81 - 84

⁵ AV Dicey, Introduction to the Study of the Law of Constitution (8th edn, Macmillan 1915) 120
<http://files.libertyfund.org/files/1714/0125_Bk.pdf> accessed 14 April 2025

⁶ DennisDominic Adjei, *Constitutional Law of Ghana: Evolution, Theory and Practice* (1 edn, Buck Press Ltd 2021) 92

⁷ Selikem Donkor, 'Permissible Positive Discrimination in a Just Society: A Social Pact of Equals' (*Ghana Law Hub*, 15 July 2024)

<[⁸ 1992 Constitution of Ghana, article 17. See also, RaymondAkongburo Atuguba, *The New Constitutional and Administrative Law of Ghana: From the Garden of Eden to 2022* \(1st edn, UG Press 2022\) 634](https://ghanalawhub.com/permissible-positive-discrimination-in-a-just-society-a-social-pact-of-equals/#:~:text=The%20constitutional%20prescription%20in%20Article.in%20Article%2012(2).> accessed 15 April 2025</p></div><div data-bbox=)

non-discrimination. This principle is universal and finds expression in the Constitution of almost every country.”⁹

This ideal has motivated the courts and quasi-judicial bodies alike in their enforcement of human rights and fundamental freedoms eloquently enshrined under the Constitution. In *Ghana Commercial Bank v The Commissioner, CHRAJ*¹⁰, the appellant bank terminated the complainant’s employment as a manager of the bank for granting a loan facility above his authorised limit. In addition to the termination, the bank withheld the terminal payments and other entitlements due the complainant pending repayment of the loan by the customer. It was found that other managers had granted similar facilities far in excess of the amount the complainant granted, yet they were not subjected to the same disciplinary action as was meted out to the complainant.

Before the Supreme Court, the issue had to be determined, inter alia, whether the termination and withholding of entitlements of the complainant was unfair and discriminatory. It was held that the differential treatment regarding the enforcement of the appellant bank’s internal rules were harsh, unfair and discriminatory. In outright disapproval of the appellant’s actions, Brobbey JSC noted:

“... [I]t became apparent that the complainant had been treated differently but more harshly from other managers for much less breach of the rules of the appellant. By definition, a person is said to have been discriminated against where he is treated differently on grounds of race, color or religion. Granting that there are clear rules on the granting of loans, the appellant should have been able to explain to the Commission or the High Court why, in spite of the existence of those clear rules, those other managers who had committed what prima facie amounted to worse breaches of the rules were not merely left off the hook but were also allowed to continue working as if what they did was nothing at all. In the absence of any explanation, the Commission, the High Court and the Court of Appeal were obviously right in concluding that the termination of the appointment of the complainant was indeed discriminatory.”¹¹

The decision emphasizes the general principle that institutions– whether public or private– are prohibited from operating systems that apply rules inconsistently or discriminatorily to employees or individuals. The Constitution mandates equality before the law, and thus, any system that creates different standards for different individuals would, without just and lawful cause, be unconstitutionally discriminatory.

The Scope of Discrimination

To discriminate, in terms of article 17(3) of the Constitution, is “*to give different treatment to different persons attributable only or mainly to their respective descriptions by race, occupation, religion or creed, whereby persons of one description are subjected to disabilities or restrictions*

⁹ Report of the Committee of Experts (Constitution) on Proposals for a Draft Constitution of Ghana Presented to the PNDC (1991) 64 [137] <<https://repository.parliament.gh/handle/123456789/1546>> (accessed 14 April 2025)

¹⁰ *Ghana Commercial Bank Ltd vs. The Commissioner, CHRAJ* [2003]DLSC2387

<[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2003\]DLSC2387&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2003]DLSC2387&srb=>) (accessed 15 April 2025)

¹¹ *Ibid.*, (Brobbey JSC)

to which persons of another description are not made subjects or are granted privileges or advantages which are not granted to persons of another description.” In simple terms, it is any differential treatment, exclusion or preference based on the protected grounds or any unlawful cause. However, it is not enough to allege the differential treatment on the prohibited grounds *simpliciter*. To amount to discrimination, the differential treatment must have the demonstrable purpose or effect of negating or impeding the recognition, enjoyment, or exercise of all rights and freedoms by all persons on an equal basis”.¹²

It must also be noted that discrimination can either be direct, indirect or both.¹³ Direct discrimination occurs when under the same or comparable circumstances, a person is treated less favourably than others in the same group. This form of discrimination is often easier to spot, as it tends to be evident on the face of the rule or conduct in question. On the other hand, indirect discrimination is not easily identifiable. In this type of discrimination, the impugned conduct, policy or rule may appear, at face value, as routine, neutral or cosmetically helpful, but will have the discriminatory effect of impairing the rights of an individual or group without any legitimate cause.

This shows that delineating the boundaries of discrimination is far from straightforward, particularly when it takes the form of the more subtle, indirect, and therefore less overt, type. Thus, there is the need for a ‘yardstick’ to determine the sweep of an infringement of the right to equality and non-discrimination. The Canadian case of *Peel Law Association v Pieters*¹⁴ offers a three-pronged objective test in determining what amounts to discrimination. The facts of the case are that the appellants, two lawyers and an articling law student were in the lawyer lounge of the respondent law association to which only lawyers and law students were permitted access. All the three respondents were black. The librarian whose duty included enforcing the policy of restriction of access to only lawyers and law students approached the appellants and demanded that they produce identification, but did not ask anyone else in the lounge. On an application by the appellants before the Human Rights Tribunal that they had been subjected to a discriminatory treatment based on their race or colour, the Ontario Court of Appeal laid down the test for determining what would amount to a *prima facie* discrimination in the following terms:

*“To find discrimination, the Vice-Chair had to be satisfied, after considering all the evidence, [1] that the appellants were members of a group protected by the Code; [2] that they were subjected to adverse treatment; and [3] that their race and colour were factors in the adverse treatment.”*¹⁵

¹² See UN Human Rights Committee (HRC), CCPR General Comment No. 18: Non-discrimination (point 6), 10 November 1989 <<https://www.refworld.org/legal/general/hrc/1989/en/6268>> accessed 15 April, 2025

¹³ ReneeAK Morhe and AbenaAgyeiwaa Asare, 'Pregnancy Discrimination as a Cause of Action In Ghana: A Commentary on CHRAJ, Grace Fosu & Thelma Hammond v Ghana National Fire Service & Attorney-General' [2021] 1(Issue 2) UCC Law Journal <<https://journal.ucc.edu.gh/index.php/ucclj/article/view/420/254>> accessed 16 April 2025

¹⁴ *Peel Law Association v. Pieters*, 2013 ONCA 396. <<https://ca.vlex.com/vid/peel-law-assoc-v-680936357>> accessed 16 April 20125

¹⁵ *Ibid*, [126]

Put differently, the test requires an applicant in a human rights action to adduce sufficient evidence to show, on the balance of probabilities¹⁶, first, that they are protected by the relevant law on non-discrimination. Transposed to the Ghanaian constitutional jurisprudence, this *onus* may be discharged by showing that the applicant possesses a characteristic associated with one or more of the protected grounds enumerated under article 17 of the Constitution.¹⁷

Secondly, the applicant must prove that they have been subjected to an adverse treatment. An adverse treatment may be any form of differential treatment that has unfavourable outcomes on the applicant such as nullifying or impairing the recognition or enjoyment of the applicant's rights or freedoms. It must be stated here that the operative consideration is the effect of the action in question, irrespective of the cause, intent, or underlying motivation. Thus, it is not necessary to demonstrate an intention or motive to discriminate. The focus is on the effect of the respondent's action on the applicant.

Finally, the applicant ought to prove that any of the protected grounds mentioned under the first limb of the test was a factor in the adverse treatment. In other words, this proof requires a connection, however tenuous, to be made between the adverse treatment and the ground of discrimination. Needless to say, the exact sweep of this layer of the test appears somewhat unclear but it was held by the learned judges of the Court of Appeal that the prohibited ground(s) need not be the cause, sole or predominant factor leading to the adverse treatment. It suffices if they are a factor or operative element in the discriminatory conduct.

Applying the test as expounded above, the court held that the librarian's conduct constituted discrimination and thus awarded the appellants damages for injury to their dignity.

This triadic test provides an objective and adaptable standard for assessing claims of unlawful discrimination. Its cogency and persuasive utility were recognized and adopted by Yeboah JA in *CHRAJ v GNFS & Attorney-General*.¹⁸

In this case, the applicants, two female fire service personnel, were dismissed from their positions on the basis of a regulation within the Ghana National Fire Service (GNFS). This regulation permitted the GNFS to dismiss females who became pregnant within their first three years of employment. Dissatisfied with this decision, the applicants filed an action, seeking a declaration that the said regulation was discriminatory and consequently for reinstatement and damages for their wrongful dismissals. The court found that the enforcement of the regulation was selective, as evidence showed that the GNFS had previously permitted other women who became pregnant within the same three-year period to return to work in modified roles.

The defence of the GNFS was that the initial three years of employment involved intense training, which could pose significant health risks to both pregnant women and their developing

¹⁶ This is the general standard of proof for all civil actions. See generally, section 12 of the Evidence Act, 1975 (NRCD 323)

¹⁷ These include race, gender, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed, social or economic status, political opinions or occupation.

¹⁸ *CHRAJ, Grace Fosu & Thelma Hammond v Ghana National Fire Service & Attorney-General*, High Court (Suit No. HR 0063 / 2017)

<<https://www.studocu.com/row/document/ghana-communication-technology-university/law-in-ghana/chraj-fire-service-ruling/109345222>> accessed 16 April 2025

fetuses. They also maintained that all employees, including the applicants, were informed of the regulations, inclusive of the restriction imposed by the impugned regulation, upon joining the fire service. The court, applying the *Peel*¹⁹ test held that the regulation was indeed discriminatory in its effect. It observed that the applicants were protected by article 17 based on their gender or sex; that their right to family life had been restricted, and this adverse treatment was solely because they were women.

An important observation from this case is the argument raised by the GNFS that the applicants had prior knowledge of the restrictions placed on them by impugned regulation. This argument²⁰ invites further analysis for two important legal principles it invokes—the equitable principle of estoppel²¹ and the doctrine of freedom of contracts²². The effect of the argument regarding the principle of freedom of contract implies that the applicants freely and voluntarily accepted recruitment by the GNFS, having known beforehand the terms and conditions of the bargain, including the impugned regulation. Therefore, they ought to be bound by those terms.

This argument looks attractive and appears, on the surface, to be in conformity with the doctrines of freedom and sanctity of contracts. However, it is not convincing as it overlooks other equally important principles of contract law and has the tendency of whittling away constitutionally guaranteed rights without caution. The flaw in the argument is its failure to acknowledge the trite fact that employers usually have the upper hand in the negotiation of employment contracts. Oftentimes, many employees simply bow to the whims and caprices of their employers because they simply have to keep up with it to earn their daily bread. This is not surprising given the high level of unemployment in Ghana.²³

The equitable principle of unconscionability therefore permits the courts to intervene to grant relief in circumstances where it may be apparent from the nature and terms of the contract that it was one to which no man in his right senses would make on the one hand, and no honest and fair man would accept on the other.²⁴ Accordingly, it is humbly submitted that it cannot be tenable for an employee to waive their protection by the Constitution to be free from unlawful discrimination and thus, the rejection of the argument was not only appropriate but aligns with well-established legal and equitable principles.

On the principle of estoppel, the argument appears to have this effect: that by committing to the terms of the GNFS including the impugned regulation, they were barred in equity from rescinding the agreement. However, it is a classic constitutional principle that the equitable

¹⁹ *Peel Law Association v. Pieters*, 2013 ONCA 396.

²⁰ It is apparent from the judgment that the court rejected the argument outrightly without an analysis of the issue raised by it.

²¹ This doctrine bars a party from asserting a right that contradicts what they have previously said or done.

²² The doctrine of freedom of contracts holds that men of full age and competent understanding are capable of determining their own interests and making their own bargain. Thus, if they freely and voluntarily enter into a contract, such contract must be held sacred and enforced by the courts. See *Printing & Numerical Co v Sampson* (1875) LR 19 Eq 462, 465 (Jessel MR)

²³ The average rate of unemployment rose to 14.7% during the first three quarters of 2023. See, Daniel Oduro-Mensah, 'Ghana's unemployment rate hits 14.7 percent' (*Citi News Room*, 21 February 2024) <<https://citinewsroom.com/2024/02/ghanas-unemployment-rate-hits-14-7-percent/>> accessed 17 April 2025

²⁴ Christine Dowuona-Hammond, *The Law of Contract in Ghana* (1st edn, Frontiers Printing & Publishing Ltd 2016) 245

principle of estoppel cannot operate to defeat constitutional rights. Article 1(2) of the Constitution places the Constitution on a pedestal high above any law of the land. Therefore, any law, order, rule or regulation which is found to be at cross-purpose(s) with any provision of the Constitution is declared void to the extent of that inconsistency. In the oft-cited case of *Tuffuor v Attorney-General*²⁵, the Court of Appeal sitting as the Supreme Court was faced with the issue of whether or not Justice Apaloo's acceptance of the nomination and appearance before Parliament for vetting could be deemed as a waiver of his constitutional immunities. Sowah JSC in outright rejection of the argument held:

*“This court does not think that any act or conduct which is contrary to the express or implied provisions of the Constitution can be validated by equitable doctrines of estoppel. No person can make lawful what the Constitution says is unlawful. No person can make unlawful what the Constitution says is lawful. The conduct must conform to due process of law as laid down in the fundamental law of the land or it is unlawful and invalid.”*²⁶

It is worth mentioning, however, that there are circumstances under which the consent or conduct of the applicant may operate to defeat their claim of human right infringement.²⁷ Nonetheless, the author submits that, like many other rights, an infringement of the right to equality and non-discrimination cannot be justified by the consent of the applicant. The limited contexts in which an applicant's consent or conduct may undermine a claim of rights infringement are exceptions only and they depend largely on the nature and function of such rights.

The right to privacy and data protection, for example, is personal and centrally seeks to protect the individual autonomy of the applicant. With this, it is not difficult to understand that in certain contexts, the applicant may be deemed to have voluntarily relinquished or modified their constitutional right to privacy and data protection. Equality and non-discrimination are structural guarantees that function independently of the will of the individual. They are grounded in the constitutional imperative to ensure the subjection of all classes to the law and to dismantle systemic barriers to participation in social, cultural and public life. Consent cannot be used to validate practices that, by their nature, perpetuate inequality or institutional bias—especially where such consent is given in a context of limited bargaining power, cultural pressure, or institutional asymmetry.

In *New Patriotic Party v Inspector-General of Police*,²⁸ Bamford Addo JSC urged the courts and human rights tribunals alike to eschew an interpretation of any kind which seeks to tamper

²⁵ *Tuffuor v Attorney-General* [1980] GLR 637

²⁶ *Ibid*, 656 (Sowah JSC)

²⁷ For example, the right to privacy and data protection as provided for under article 18(2) of the Constitution and the Data Protection Act, 2012 (Act 843) respectively, are personal in nature and partly dependent on the conduct of the data subject. Thus, an individual who expressly or impliedly consents to a privacy-infringing act may be deemed to have waived the protection otherwise available. See, Data Protection Act, 2012 (Act 843), s 20; *Francis Kwarteng Arthur v Ghana Telecommunications Co. Ltd.* [2021]DLHC10759 <[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2021\]DLHC10759&sr=2&court=hc](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2021]DLHC10759&sr=2&court=hc)> accessed 17 April 2025

²⁸ *New Patriotic Party v Inspector-General of Police* [1993-94] GLR 459

with the fundamental human rights, but to interpret and enforce constitutional rights and freedoms generously and purposively to advance democratic values.

It follows, therefore, that it is an untenable defence to a claim of discrimination that an applicant merely failed to comply with internal institutional rules. Internal rules must themselves be free from discriminatory content or effect, and their implementation must adhere to principles of non-discrimination.²⁹ A rule that appears neutral but results in the disproportionate treatment of certain individuals may still amount to indirect discrimination and cannot be justified by mere reference to internal compliance.

Positive Discrimination

It is now a universal principle that the right to equality and non-discrimination is not an inflexible rule. The United Nations Human Rights Committee has noted that “[t]he enjoyment of rights and freedoms on an equal footing, however, does not mean identical treatment in every instance.”³⁰

This idea finds expression in the trite principle that human rights are not absolute. Laws are generally made to reflect the realities of the society and thus, where the societal structure so demands, some form of legitimate interference is to be allowed in order to ensure that the protection of individual rights does not undermine broader societal interests. Article 12(2) of the Constitution which begins the substantive human rights provisions provides that:

“Every person in Ghana, whatever his place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual ... but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.”

The language of this provision evokes an understanding that the underlying philosophy which animates the relevant provisions is that the rights are fluid and dynamic.³¹ Thus, it subjects the enjoyment of the rights to two general limitations—respect for the rights of others and the public interest.

In determining whether a limitation on a constitutional right is justified, the courts undertake a balancing exercise that weighs the interests of society against those of the individual, with the aim of promoting good governance directed at the rapid socio-economic, political, and cultural development of the Republic.³² Through this exercise a two-tier test has been established to determine the validity of any statutory or other limitation placed on a constitutional right.³³

²⁹ See *Ghana Commercial Bank Ltd vs. The Commissioner*; CHRAJ [2003]DLSC2387 (Brobbeey JSC) <[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2003\]DLSC2387&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2003]DLSC2387&srb=>) (accessed 15 April 2025)

³⁰ UN Human Rights Committee (HRC), CCPR General Comment No. 18: Non-discrimination, 10 November 1989 [8] <<https://www.refworld.org/legal/general/hrc/1989/en/6268>> accessed 17 April 2025

³¹ Kofi Kumado, *A Handbook of the Constitutional Law of Ghana and Its History* (1 edn, Black Mask Ltd 2021) 217

³² Seth Yeboa Bimpong-Buta, *The Role of the Supreme Court in the Development of Constitutional Law in Ghana* (LLD thesis, University of South Africa 2005) 457. See also, *Republic v Tommy Thompson Books Ltd, Quarcoo & Coomson* [1996-97] SCGLR 804, 846 (Kpegah JSC)

³³ *Ahumah Ocansey v Electoral Commission and Centre For Human Rights & Civil Liberties v The Attorney-General & Anor. (Consolidated)* [2010]DLSC6138

<[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2010\]DLSC6138&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2010]DLSC6138&srb=>) accessed 18 April 2025.

This test, otherwise known as the *Oakes*³⁴ test, requires that, first, the limitation be reasonably necessary or required in the public interest. This implies that the objective of the limiting law or action must be of such sufficient importance as to justify a limitation on a constitutionally protected right or freedom. The objective of that limitation must not be trivial or frivolous, but must be sufficiently important.

The second prong of the test requires that the limitation must be a rational and proportionate means of achieving the stated objective. This would involve an examination of the provisions of the limiting law to determine *inter alia*, whether due process is followed, and whether they unduly impair the constitutional right.

In *Civil and Local Government Staff Association of Ghana (CLOGSAG) vs. Attorney General and Others*³⁵, Akuffo JSC (as she then was) captured the test in the following terms:

“[I]n determining the validity of any statutory or other limitation placed on a constitutional right, the questions that need to be determined are:

a. Is the limitation necessary? In other words, is the limitation necessary for the enhancement of democracy and freedoms of all, is it for the public good?

b. Is the limitation proportional? Is the limitation over-broad such as to effectively nullify a particular right or freedom guaranteed by the constitution?”

Thus, for any limitation to individual rights to be valid, the limitation must be prescribed by law; it must be reasonably necessary in a democratic society and must also be proportional to the objective which is sought to be achieved.³⁶

This means that a finding of discrimination *simpliciter* may not be enough to ground a successful claim of human rights infringement. Where the discriminatory impact of a law or administrative action can be shown to be reasonably necessary for the advancement of a legitimate public interest, and proportionate to the objective pursued, such differential treatment is constitutionally justifiable.

This kind of discrimination is referred to as *positive discrimination*³⁷ and is supported by article 17(4) of the Constitution which authorizes Parliament to enact laws that are reasonably necessary to, *inter alia*, implement policies and programmes aimed at redressing socio-economic or educational imbalance in the Ghanaian society and to make provision for different communities based on their special circumstances.

³⁴ R. v. Oakes, [1986] 1 S.C.R. 103. The term originates from Canadian constitutional jurisprudence, but its structure has been adopted, in substance, by the Ghanaian courts.

³⁵ *Civil and Local Government Staff Association of Ghana (CLOGSAG) vs. Attorney General and Others* [2017] DLSC 2590 <[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2017\]DLSC2590&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2017]DLSC2590&srb=>) accessed 18 April 2025

³⁶ Kofi Kumado, *A Handbook of the Constitutional Law of Ghana and Its History* (1 edn, Black Mask Ltd 2021) 217-218

³⁷ It allows preferential treatment or opportunities to individuals or groups that have been historically disadvantaged or underrepresented in order to redress systemic inequalities.

It is therefore incumbent on a person who alleges discrimination by virtue of acts done under the authority of an Act of Parliament to show that either the Act of Parliament or the conduct complained of falls outside the scope of constitutionally permitted limitations.

The Supreme Court was presented with a historic opportunity to define the contours of the right to equality and non-discrimination, and to clarify the legitimate scope of positive discrimination under the Constitution, in what has become the *locus classicus* on the subject—*Nartey v Gati*³⁸. In this case, the plaintiff contested the constitutionality of section 30(1) of the Legal Profession Act, 1960 (Act 32) which prohibits a lawyer from suing their client for legal fees until after the expiration of one month after notifying the client debtor. He contended that the said provision was discriminatory of lawyers by reason only of their profession. Thus, it was contrary to article 17 of the Constitution and the same must be struck down as void. In its unanimous ruling, the Supreme Court held that section 30(1) of Act 32 did not contravene article 17. The Court speaking through Date-Bah JSC noted as follows:

“If the law were to treat all human beings rigidly equally, it would in fact result in unequal outcomes. Rigid equal treatment would often result in unfair and unequal results. Accordingly, it is widely recognized that equality before the law requires equal treatment of those similarly placed, implying different treatment in respect of those with different characteristics. In simple terms, equals must be treated equally, while the treatment of unequals must be different. The law must be able to differentiate between unequals and accord them the differentiated treatment which will result in enabling them, as far as practicable, to attain the objective of equality of outcomes or of fairness. In effect, equality of opportunity will often entail the law treating people differently in order to give them a fighting chance of attaining equality of outcomes or of fairness. If the differentiated legal rights arising from such an approach to the law were to be struck down as not conforming with the constitutional prescription that all persons are equal before the law, it would be thoroughly counterproductive.”

In coming to this conclusion, the court was motivated by the fact it is simply impracticable that every person within the Ghanaian jurisdiction has, or must have, exactly the same rights as all other persons in the jurisdiction. As has been observed by Kulendi JSC in *Gorni Vrs The Attorney-general & Anor*,³⁹ the Constitution has, in its express and implied terms, restricted the enjoyment of certain rights by specific persons such as chiefs, judges, members of the Electoral Commission and of the Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice. These are not unjustified restrictions. They are necessary due to their status and the respective offices they occupy in the society. Similarly, the Constitution itself accords certain rights to some class of persons that others outside that class may not be entitled to. The fact that they have such rights does not mean that they are in breach of article 17. The crucial issue, therefore, in any discrimination action is “*whether the differentiation in rights is justifiable, by reference to an*

³⁸ *T. T. Nartey v Godwin Gati* [2010] DLSC4143

<[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2010\]DL.SC4143&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2010]DL.SC4143&srb=>) accessed 19 April 2025

³⁹ *Gorni Vrs The Attorney-general & Anor* [2022] GHASC 95 (1 November 2022)

<<https://ghalii.org/akn/gh-hr-accra/judgment/ghasc/2022/95/eng@2022-11-01>> accessed 19 April 2025

object that is sought to be served by a particular statute, constitutional provision or some other rule of law."⁴⁰

The Court in *Nartey v Gati* gave a judicial endorsement to the concept of permissible differentiation. This is commendable as it allows lawful distinctions to be drawn between persons based on relevant attributes or functions, as long as these distinctions pursue a legitimate aim and are proportionate. Much as there must be equal protection by the law of everyone, it will not only be counter-intuitive but normatively unsettling to treat the right to equality and freedom from discrimination as a *jus cogens* norm.

The true essence of equality must allow derogation and limitation, provided that the derogation is necessary, minimal and enures to an inevitable public gain that otherwise could not reasonably be achieved. Therefore, the textual reinterpretation by Date-Bah JSC⁴¹ of the constitutional slogan from "all persons shall be equal before the law" to "equals must be treated equally by the law" is as instructive as it will remain increasingly true.

The author opines that the reasoning of the court in *Nartey v Gati* is firmly anchored within the Ghanaian constitutional framework as it shuns *carte blanche* equality. Once more, it is responsive to the trenchant call Sowah JSC made in the celebrated case of *Tuffuor v Attorney-General*⁴² that in the interpretation of the Constitution, account must be taken of the provisions "*as landmarks in a people's search for progress.*" The Constitution contains the hopes and aspirations of the Ghanaian people for a better and fuller life. For the hopes can be achieved if the law is made permissive of legitimate differential treatment to address the systemic inequalities not only inherent but prevalent in the society.

However, it is worth noting that the reasoning, in hindsight, risks creating a slippery slope where any classification could be justified if a 'legitimate aim' is claimed. Equality and non-discrimination are central to the corpus of rights guaranteed by the Constitution. Together, the two constitute the *grundnorm* in the scheme of rights entrenched under our constitutional jurisprudence— a norm at the top which locks and holds the arch of rights in place. Once disturbed, the whole edifice—human rights and freedoms— stands shuddered. Therefore, allowing a limitation on the right to equality must be a matter of extraordinary caution. In the remaining part, the paper shall discuss two subsequent decisions of the Supreme Court wherein the concept of differential treatment was applied, with the view to assessing whether the "extraordinary caution" was taken.

A. *The Dual Citizenship Case: Asare v Attorney-General*⁴³

Section 16(2) of the Citizenship Act, 2000 (Act 591) disqualified dual citizens from holding some specified public offices. The plaintiff sought, among others, a declaration that the said section is unconstitutional and void as it contravenes, *inter alia*, article 17 of the Constitution. He argued that section 16(2) discriminates against a Ghanaian citizen who has acquired the

⁴⁰ *T. T. Nartey v Godwin Gati* [2010] DLSC4143 (Date-Bah JSC)

<[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2010\]DL.SC4143&sr=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2010]DL.SC4143&sr=>) accessed 19 April 2025

⁴¹ *Ibid*

⁴² *Tuffuor v Attorney-General* [1980] GLR 637

⁴³ *Asare Vrs Attorney General* [2012] GHASC 31 (22 May 2012)

<<https://ghalii.org/akn/gh/judgment/ghasc/2012/31/eng@2012-05-22>> accessed 19 April 2025

citizenship of another country by disqualifying dual citizens and consequently violating their political rights as citizens, as enshrined under article 55(10) of the Constitution. Relying heavily on the *Nartey v Gati* case, the Supreme Court held that excluding dual citizens from holding those specified public offices is not discriminatory.

At face value, it is not difficult to agree that the disqualification of dual citizens from holding certain public offices is discriminatory. The differential treatment is solely by reason of their social status—dual citizens. This is prohibited by the literal meaning of article 17(2) which proscribes discrimination based on social status, among other factors. However, a closer examination, guided by the instructive principle laid in *Nartey v. Gati*, reveals that even discrimination based on one's social status is not *per se* unlawful. It is unlawful if it is not for a lawful and legitimate purpose.

Thus, it was the reasonable necessity and proportionate outcome of the purpose of the impugned section which, as expected, was largely determinative of the issue whether the disqualification was unconstitutionally discriminatory.

The court found that the purpose of the disqualification is to secure allegiance and loyalty of Ghanaian citizens to the Republic. This was held to be a legitimate purpose as it is in the public interest to put in place a framework conducive to loyalty. Also, the purpose was found to be necessary as the allowance of the holding of sensitive offices by persons who owed allegiance to other countries in addition to the Republic of Ghana would run counter to article 284 of the Constitution.⁴⁴

It must be noted that the plaintiff challenged the cogency of this argument and cited examples of Justices who, while being judges in the Republic, had the opportunity of being Chief Justices and Judges in other jurisdictions and served in their respective offices with distinction. On this argument, the response of the Court (speaking through Date-Bah JSC) was in the following terms:

“This is a cogent argument. However, I do not think a court has to be persuaded by the cogency of the rationale for a legislative purpose before it can see its way clear to enforcing that purpose. A court may not necessarily agree with the logic or coherence of a particular purpose sought to be achieved by the legislature, but that is no justifiable basis for refusing to enforce the legislation that seeks to implement this purpose... Thus, bad or unsound legislative policy is not necessarily unconstitutional.”

The author opines that this response putatively aligns with the dictates of Separation of Powers, a necessary doctrine in any constitutional democracy. It, however, leaves much to be desired as it has the tendency of making meaningless the essence of the second limb of the limitation test—proportionality. Satisfying the test of proportionality requires a consideration of several factors. In *CHRAJ v GNFS & Attorney-General*⁴⁵, the court held that in order for the differential treatment to be proportional to the legitimate objective, there must be a rational connection

⁴⁴ This constitutional provision prohibits a public officer from putting himself in a position where his interest conflicts or is likely to conflict with the performance of the functions of his office.

⁴⁵ CHRAJ, Grace Fosu & Thelma Hammond v Ghana National Fire Service & Attorney-General, High Court (Suit No. HR 0063 / 2017)

between the means and the objective sought to be achieved. Can a purpose be “legitimate” if its means are irrational or logically disconnected from the aim? If there must be a necessary link between the object of the impugned law and the differentiation, then an outright dismissiveness of the logicity of the means, in the respectful opinion of the author, falls short of expectations.

In fact, logicity has been mentioned as one indicium of reasonableness⁴⁶ [and proportionality]. To qualify as a reasonable and proportional limitation, the means chosen to achieve a particular objective must be logically coherent to achieve the aim. Where the means is not apt to achieve the aim, then the inaptness of the means points to unreasonableness.

Nonetheless, the author opines, though with a reversionary caution, that the concept of differential treatment was well applied. The test of proportionality, despite the court’s response heretofore discussed, was satisfied by Atuguba JSC in his concurring opinion when he held that “*this variation in citizenship rights is not arbitrary but based on the need for security of allegiance to the state of Ghana proportionate to the type of office of state involved.*”⁴⁷ The positions specified by the impugned section⁴⁸ are, by their nature, sensitive to the security of the State. To the extent that there is an intelligible legislative classification—dual citizens— as well as a number of other public posts to which the dual nationals remain eligible, the disqualification, on a balance, is far from unconstitutional discrimination.

B. *Darlington Osae v FDA & Attorney-General*⁴⁹

In exercise of its statutory function to, among others, ensure adequate and effective standards for food and drugs, the Food and Drugs Authority (FDA) published guidelines for the advertisement of foods, paragraph 3.2.10 thereof which provided that “no well-known personality or professional shall be used in alcoholic beverage advertising.” The plaintiff instituted an action at the Supreme Court challenging the constitutionality of the said provision. He argued that the impugned guideline prevented people who have worked very hard in various fields of endeavor to build their reputation from monetizing their goodwill by advertising alcoholic products. He therefore urged the Court to strike down the said guideline as being discriminatory, unconstitutional and void. The defendants argued that well-known personalities have strong appeals on brand. The restriction was therefore necessary to protect public health by, inter alia, reducing the exposure of minors to such advertisements. In a 5-2 majority opinion⁵⁰, the Supreme Court held that the restriction was not discriminatory.

⁴⁶ Paul Daly, 'Wednesbury's Reason and Structure' [2011] (2) Public Law, 244
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Paul-Daly-8/publication/265614720_Wednesbury%27s_Reason_and_Structure/links/5566065e08aec22682ff1574/Wednesburys-Reason-and-Structure.pdf> accessed 20 April 2025

⁴⁷ *Asare Vrs Attorney General* [2012] GHASC 31 (22 May 2012), 14

⁴⁸ The list includes: Chief Justice and Justices of the Supreme Court; Ambassador or High Commissioner; Secretary to the Cabinet; Chief of Defence Staff or any Service Chief; Inspector-General of Police; Commissioner, Custom, Excise and Preventive Service; Director of Immigration Service; Commissioner, Value Added Tax Service; Director-General, Prisons Service; Chief Fire Officer; Chief Director of a Ministry; the rank of a Colonel in the Army or its equivalent in the other security services.

⁴⁹ *Osae v Food and Drugs Authority & Attorney-General* [2024] GHASC 30 (19 June 2024)
<<https://ghalii.org/akn/gh/judgment/ghasc/2024/30/eng@2024-06-19>> accessed 20 April 2025

⁵⁰ Torkornoo CJ, Baffoe-Bonnie, Owusu, Asiedu and Koomson JJSC (Ackah-Yensu and Prof Mensa-Bonsu JJSC dissenting)

The main ground upon which their lordships on the majority bench based their decision was that the plaintiff could not establish that well-known personalities or professionals who had been prohibited by the FDA from indulging in the advertisement of alcoholic beverages had been so prohibited due to their race, place of origin, political opinions, colour, gender, occupation, religion or creed. This, according to the Court, fell short of the definition of discrimination provided by article 17(3) of the Constitution.

In the opinion of the author, this reasoning seems irreconcilable with the ideals of constitutional justice. It suffers from a doctrinaire approach to interpreting the Constitution, which Sowah JSC, in his famous dictum in *Tuffour v Attorney-General*⁵¹ cautioned the courts to forbear. Article 17(2) prohibits differential treatment based on, inter alia, social status. In the ordinary sense of the term, *social status* would generally be understood as a person's position or standing in society, based on how they are perceived due to occupation, fame, family background, education, lifestyle, amongst others.

Therefore, it is not far wrong to assert that being a “well-known personality” is one's social status. Assuming *arguendo*, that “well-known personalities” do not fall within any of the prohibited groups under article 17, it must be noted that “*article 17(1) and (2) create a generic situation, and so cannot capture every conceivable class of people or grouping.*”⁵²

A fortiori, the reasoning is even more difficult to sustain when considered alongside article 33(5) of the Constitution which provides that the catalogue of rights expressly mentioned under Chapter Five of the Constitution are not exhaustive, but allows an inclusion into the sweep of rights any freedom which is inherent in a democracy and intended to secure the freedom and dignity of man.

As Francois JSC noted, “*this provision attempts an all-embracing liberal framework that would include all possible shades of freedom not specifically mentioned, but are essential cogs to enhance the driving capacity of a truly free-wheeling democracy.*”⁵³ The courts are therefore under a constitutional imperative to go beyond the express human rights provisions of the Constitution in their enforcement of rights and freedoms of the populace.

In *Dr Festus Nii Boye v Ghana Ports and Harbourous Authority*⁵⁴, the plaintiff sued for a declaration that the termination of his employment based on his medical conditions— a hypertensive and diabetic patient— was discriminatory of him. The court, in upholding his claim, instructively observed that:

“Although article 17(2) and (3) do not specifically state disability or persons living with diabetes and hypertension as grounds for discrimination, article 33(5) of the 1992 Constitution widens the scope of human rights violations... The court takes judicial notice of the fact that diabetes and hypertension affect a substantial

⁵¹ *Tuffour v Attorney-General* [1980] GLR 637, 647-648

⁵² *Osae v Food and Drugs Authority & Attorney-General* [2024] GHASC 30 (19 June 2024), 62 (Ackah-Yensu JSC)

⁵³ *New Patriotic Party v Ghana Broadcasting Corporation* [1993-1994] 2 GLR 354, 367 (Francois JSC)

⁵⁴ *Dr Festus Nii Boye v Ghana Ports and Harbourous Authority* Suit No. INDL 53/13

<<https://www.globalhealthrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/DR-FESTUS-NII-BOYE-BOYE-V-GHANA-PORTS-HARBOURS-AUTHORITY.pdf>> accessed 21 April 2025

number of the adult population the world over. Sufferers can therefore be described by their conditions as being hypertensive and or diabetic as in Plaintiff's case. Being so identified by such description, sufferers of these medical conditions qualify for protection under the Constitution not to be discriminated against on account of their medical conditions."⁵⁵

Thus, in the opinion of the author, the decision that the guideline was not discriminatory of "well-known personalities" was made *per incuriam*. The proper test for determining an infringement to a fundamental right is to examine its effect and not merely its object.⁵⁶ While it is admitted that the holistic purpose of the guidelines is, in one breadth, legitimate in the public interest, the effect of the restriction is to unjustly deny the right of persons who would have succeeded in working hard to build a reputation in an industry, either as musicians, footballers or academics from commercially exploiting their goodwill solely on account of their status as "well-known personalities". It is therefore challenging to maintain the view that the ban is non-discriminatory.

It is acknowledged, however, that this mere finding of discrimination is not sufficient to declare the impugned guideline unconstitutional. If reasonable and proportional, the restriction would be sustained as constitutionally warranted. To determine the reasonableness of a differential treatment, one factor to be determined is whether the classification is founded on an intelligible differentia which distinguishes between persons or things that are grouped together from others left out of the group.⁵⁷ In other words, the differentiation must be distillable and recognizable.

In the guideline, paragraph 3.2.10 of which was challenged, the phrase "well-known personalities" is defined to include any person who arouses sufficient interest in society. As trenchantly noted by Ackah-Yensu JSC on the minority side, "*implicit in this definition, is the recognition that not all personalities or professionals would be affected by the ban.*" The disqualification is restricted to only those who, in the opinion of the FDA, arouse sufficient interest in society. Such people may be historians, politicians, religious leaders, academics, cultural figures, celebrities and sports figures.

The author submits that this classification falls short of an intelligible differentia as is unconstitutionally vague and would potentially lead to inconsistent outcomes. The determination of "well-known personalities" from the language of the guidelines lacks an objective, predetermined criteria. The class of "well-known personalities and professions" is so amorphous that it is unclear who falls within the class. It is a constitutional principle that a law is unconstitutionally vague when people of common intelligence must necessarily guess at its meaning.⁵⁸

⁵⁵ *Ibid*, 12 (Dekeyem J)

⁵⁶ *Ahumah Ocansey v Electoral Commission and Centre for Human Rights & Civil Liberties v The Attorney-General & Anor. (Consolidated)* [2010] DLSC6138 (Wood CJ)

⁵⁷ See *T. T. Nartey v Godwin Gati* [2010] DLSC4143 (Date-Bah JSC)

⁵⁸ *Connally v General Construction Co.*, 269 US 385 [1926]; See *Tsatsu Tsikata v Republic* [2011] GHASC 3 (19 January 2011)

Inconsistency has been argued as one indicium of unreasonableness in determining the validity of a limitation to a constitutional right.⁵⁹ In the instant case, it is possible for different conclusions to be reached by the FDA with respect to similar factual situations. This, in the persuasive argument of the eminent Canadian jurist, Professor Daly, points to unreasonableness.⁶⁰

Furthermore, the amorphous language of the definition of “well-known personality” effectively vests a significant quantum of discretion in the FDA to determine who falls within the definition. Article 296(c) of the Constitution mandates the publication of regulations to govern the exercise of discretionary power. The purpose of this provision, it is argued, is to ensure fairness and candidness; and to prevent an arbitrary, capricious or biased use of that discretion. Since there are no regulations to guide the determination of well-known persons whose rights would be affected by the ban, the likelihood of arbitrariness in the application of this guideline to discriminate against persons from pursuing their economic activities is glaringly dangerous.

From the foregoing, it is troubling to understand how the majority could satisfy itself with the reasonable necessity limb of the test. The author submits, with great deference, that the restriction is unreasonable and thus not necessary. It must be noted that **both** limbs of the two-pronged limitation test—reasonable necessity and proportionality must be satisfied in order to pass the limitation test.⁶¹ Having argued that the restriction on “well-known personality” from advertising alcoholic beverages is unnecessary, the author will, for the purpose of space, not assess the restriction vis-a-vis the proportionality prong. For a finding that the restriction is not reasonably necessary is, in itself, sufficient to dispose of the question whether the measure is unlawfully discriminatory.

Conclusion

Glaring patterns of inequality manifests themselves in different forms in the Ghanaian society. A substantial body of research has documented a pronounced disparity in economic development and quality of life between the northern and southern regions of the country, with Northern Ghana consistently exhibiting lower levels across various indicators.⁶² There is also a sharp urban-rural divide of the narrative. The patterns indicate a discernible advantage in living standards within urbanized regions compared to rural districts. Even within certain rural areas, disparities in resource endowments and access to services have produced subtle yet important forms of inequality.

These geographic and economic disparities are further compounded by the persistence of other forms of invidious discrimination entrenched in the fabric of the Ghanaian society. These include discrimination based on race, ethnicity, income-levels and relative status in society,

⁵⁹ Paul Daly, 'Wednesbury's Reason and Structure' [2011] (2) Public Law, 244

⁶⁰ *Ibid*

⁶¹ See *Ahumah Ocansey v Electoral Commission and Centre For Human Rights & Civil Liberties v The Attorney-General & Anor. (Consolidated)* [2010]DLSC6138 <[https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=\[2010\]DLSC6138&srb=>](https://www.dennislawgh.com/case-preview?dl_citation_no=[2010]DLSC6138&srb=>) accessed 18 April 2025.

⁶² Dzodzi Tsikata and Wayo Seini, *Identities, Inequalities and Conflicts in Ghana* (CRISE Working Paper No 5, Centre for Research on Inequality, Human Security and Ethnicity, University of Oxford 2004) 6 <<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/57a08cbbe5274a31e00013e0/wp5.pdf>> accessed 20 April 2025.

gender, and disability. This unfortunate development brings to the fore the important role the law can—and must—play in dismantling these deeply entrenched biases, which continue to impede social justice in Ghana.

The Constitution contains well-intentioned and excellent human rights provisions which, if fully enforced, could decisively drive our quest to socioeconomic development and constitutional justice.⁶³ However, the realization of this potential demands a progressive and purposive interpretation of the *grundnorm* of rights—equality and non-discrimination. It is submitted that achieving substantive equality, non-discrimination, and an equitable distribution of the benefits and burdens of development requires that legal and policy frameworks begin from a presumption of equal treatment.⁶⁴ However, this formal equality must be complemented by an equity-sensitive approach in both legislation and adjudication—one that acknowledges and addresses the historical and systemic socio-economic asymmetries.

Nonetheless, such differential treatments must be recognized as exceptions to the general rule of equal treatment. As such, they must always be grounded in law, demonstrably necessary, and proportionate to the legitimate objectives they seek to achieve. Article 17(4) of the Constitution provides a lawful framework for such exceptions. Yet to prevent a dissonance within the constitutional order, its application must reflect a structural harmony with the guarantees of equality and liberty under the preceding clauses of the said article.

The operationalization of article 17(4) must therefore ensure that any measures adopted to redress imbalances also respect, as far as practicable, the rights and dignity of all. The appropriate standard, then, should not merely be whether inequality exists, but whether such differential treatment benefits everyone.

As Rawls puts it, “[i]njustice is simply inequalities that are not to the benefit of all... If certain inequalities of wealth and differences in authority would make everyone better off than in this hypothetical starting situation [of equal liberties for all], then they accord with the general conception of justice.”⁶⁵ The challenge for Parliament, policymakers and the courts are, therefore, to design and assess remedial measures under article 17(4) in a manner that requires such provisions to be temporary, reviewable and targeted. These measures must be justified by measurable improvements in the prospects of disadvantaged groups and must not impose disproportionate costs on others. This is how the Constitution’s promise of equality can be pursued while still preserving its guarantee of liberty.

The legal and constitutional order of Ghana did not emerge in a historical vacuum. The colonial legacy of uneven development, the centralization of power and resources, and the privileging of certain regions and social classes over others have left enduring imprints on the constitutional and socio-economic architecture of the country. These structural imbalances have been sustained, and in some instances deepened, by post-independence policies that have not always prioritized equity. The consequences are evident in access to education, healthcare, infrastructure and political voice, particularly among communities historically marginalized by geography or social

⁶³ Raymond A Atuguba, *Ghana Developing Through Law* [2005] 1(9) IEA Policy Analysis

⁶⁴ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (rev edn, Harvard University Press 1990) 56

⁶⁵ *ibid*, 54-55

status. Any genuine commitment to justice must therefore reckon with this history, not as a matter of historical grievance, but as a constitutional imperative.

Arguably, this is what informed the framers of the 1992 Constitution in their drafting of article 17(4) to contain and gradually dismantle the imbalances. It blesses the notion that an equity-sensitive approach to legislation and adjudication does not discard the principle of equal treatment but recognizes that equality sometimes requires differential measures to produce fair outcomes. The role of law, then, is to function not only as a constraint on arbitrary power but as a facilitator of structural inclusion. This requires laws that do not merely prohibit discrimination but actively dismantle the barriers that perpetuate exclusion. The constitutional guarantees must be interpreted and applied purposively to ensure that claims to equality are not used to entrench privilege or frustrate necessary reforms. In this way, the path to development becomes one of constitutional fidelity, measured not solely by growth, but by the broad and equitable distribution of its benefits.